

Supplementary Figure S7. Cholera toxin (CT) production for WT, $\Delta aceE$, $\Delta aceF$, and $\Delta toxT$ strains. CT values relative to optical density (pg/mL/OD₆₀₀) are reported under standard AKI toxin-inducing conditions (A-F) and anaerobic AKI conditions (G-H). (A-F) CT levels were measured at 4h, 5h, 6h, 7h, 8h, and 24h. (G-H) CT levels were measured at 8h and 24h. The optical densities for the biological replicates are displayed below the corresponding strain on the x-axis. Data represent the average and SEM for three biological replicates. Panel G is a duplicate graph of Figure 3B and is included here for convenient comparison with the 24h timepoint.